

Oxidative kinetics of serine and threonine by *N*-bromonicotinamide

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidative decarboxylation and deamination of α -amino acids, namely, serine and threonine by *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN) in aqueous acetic acid medium (1 : 1) in presence of hydrochloric acid was studied over the temperature range 308–328 K. The oxidation reaction leads to the formation of corresponding aldehydes, CO₂ and NH₃. The reaction does not induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. The reaction was found to be first order with respect to substrate concentration. Inverse first order was observed with respect to concentration of oxidant and mineral acid. Added nicotinamide retarded the reaction. Mercuric acetate had no significant effect on the reaction rate. A decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate. HOBr has been postulated as the reactive oxidizing species in the reaction. The activation parameters were evaluated.

Keywords : Serine, threonine, *N*-bromonicotinamide, kinetics, oxidation, mechanism.

Introduction

The oxidation of amino acids is of interest due to their biological importance. Amino acids play a significant role in a number of metabolic reactions. Specific metabolic roles of amino acids include the biosynthesis of polypeptides and proteins and the synthesis of nucleotides. Thus the mechanism of analogous non-enzymatic chemical processes in the oxidation of amino acids is a potential area for intensive investigations¹.

Amino acids have been oxidized by a variety of oxidizing agents^{2–4}. Different products have been identified by different workers^{5–8} on the oxidation of amino acids. The study of amino acids becomes important because of their biological significance and selectivity towards the oxidant to yield different products. The mode of oxidation of amino acids is not only biochemically important but also helps in better understanding of their reducing properties in solutions.

A detailed investigation of the kinetics of the oxidation of serine and threonine by a newly developed oxidant *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN)⁹ in aqueous acetic acid medium in the presence of hydrochloric acid is reported in this paper. It is a mild, efficient, stable and less expensive oxidant. It possesses antimicrobial activity against *E. coli*, *Solmonella enterocolitica*, *Shigella flexneri* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. It is found to have pharmacological activity in general, CNS (central nervous system) stimulant activity in particular.

Results and discussion

The kinetic results can be summarized as follows. The rate data are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of variation of [HCl], [NBN], [Sub] on reaction rate

[NaClO ₄] = 0.1 mol dm ⁻³ , H ₂ O : CH ₃ COOH (1 : 1), Hg(CH ₃ COO) ₂ = 0.005 mol dm ⁻³ , Temp = 308 K		
Variation [Sub] = 0.04 mol dm ⁻³ [NBN] = 0.004 mol dm ⁻³		
[HCl] mol dm ⁻³	Ser k_{obs} 10 ⁵ s ⁻¹	Thr k_{obs} 10 ⁵ s ⁻¹
0.8	10.71	10.92
0.9	10.00	10.35
1.0	9.28	9.82
1.1	8.71	9.33
[Sub] 10 ² mol dm ⁻³ [HCl] 0.8 mol dm ⁻³ [NBN] 0.004 mol dm ⁻³		
4.0	10.71	10.92
5.0	10.97	11.18
6.0	11.16	11.37
7.0	11.28	11.49
8.0	11.56	11.77
[NBN] 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³ [Sub] 0.04 mol dm ⁻³ [HCl] 0.8 mol dm ⁻³		
4.0	10.71	10.92
5.0	10.40	10.60
6.0	10.18	10.39
7.0	10.01	10.21
8.0	9.91	10.12

The kinetic studies were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions with [amino acid] >> [NBN].

Effect of varying [oxidant] :

The oxidation was carried out with different initial concentrations of NBN. The pseudo-first order rate constants decrease with increase in the initial concentration of the oxidant. But in each kinetic run, the reaction shows no deviation whatsoever from the first order plot.

Effect of varying [amino acid] :

At constant $[H^+]$, with the [amino acid] in excess, the plot of $\log (E_t - E_\infty)$ (where E_t is the e.m.f. of the cell at time t and E_∞ , the corresponding value at the completion of the reaction) vs time is linear, indicating a first order dependence of rate on [NBN]. Increase in [amino acid] has a slight positive effect on the rate, indicating first order dependence of rate on [amino acid]¹.

Effect of varying $[H^+]$:

The rates decreased with increase in $[H^+]$, at fixed [NBN] and [amino acid], with varying inverse order dependence in $[H^+]$.

Effect of variation of dielectric constant of the medium :

An increase in the rate constant is noticed on decreasing the dielectric constant of the medium. Plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ ($r = 0.9901$), where D is the dielectric constant of the medium, gives straight line with positive slope¹⁰. The reaction rate increased with an increase in the percentage of acetic acid, suggesting that a low dielectric medium favors the oxidation¹¹. Amis has shown that a plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ gives a straight line, with a positive slope for a reaction between a cation and a dipole. This concept agrees with the present observations, where a positive ion and a dipole are involved in the rate limiting step of Scheme 1⁷.

Table 2. Effect of variation of $[CH_3COOH : H_2O]$ on reaction rate

[Sub] = 0.04 mol dm⁻³, [NBN] = 0.004 mol dm⁻³, [HCl] = 0.8 mol dm⁻³, [NaClO₄] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, Hg(CH₃COO)₂ = 0.005 mol dm⁻³, temp = 308 K

CH ₃ COOH (%)	H ₂ O (%)	D	10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	
			Ser	Thr
50	50	37.50	10.71	10.92
55	45	34.75	12.41	12.62
60	40	31.50	14.37	14.59
65	35	28.50	16.61	16.82

Effect of addition of nicotinamide :

The rate of reaction decreases on adding nicotinamide (NA). Thus added nicotinamide has a retarding effect on the rate of oxidation. Further the plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs [NA] is linear indicating inverse dependence of rate on [NA]¹². Addition of salts like Na₂SO₄ to the reaction medium has no effect on the rate.

No polymerization is observed when acrylonitrile is added to the reaction mixture thus ruling out radical oxidation. Increase in temperature increases the rate of oxidation and plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs reciprocal of temperature is linear. The oxidation of serine and threonine was studied at different temperatures (308 to 328 K) and the activation parameters were evaluated (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of temperature on reaction rate

[Sub] = 0.04 mol dm⁻³, [NBN] = 0.004 mol dm⁻³, [HCl] = 0.8 mol dm⁻³, [NaClO₄] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, H₂O : CH₃COOH (1 : 1), Hg(CH₃COO)₂ = 0.005 mol dm⁻³

Temp. (K)	10 ⁵ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	
	Ser	Thr
308	10.71	10.92
313	12.72	12.93
318	15.09	15.29
323	17.86	18.06
328	21.11	21.32

Activation parameters

Substrate	E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
	(kJ mol ⁻¹)			
Ser	14.90	12.34	-178.87	67.41
Thr	14.76	12.20	-179.26	67.41

Mechanism :

The possible oxidizing species in acidified aqueous acetic acid solution are NBN, NBNH⁺, NBNBr, Br₂, HOBr, H₂OBr⁺¹³.

The observed first order dependence of the reaction rate on NBN rules out NBNBr and molecular bromine as the reactive oxidizing species. NBNH⁺ and H₂OBr may be discarded because of inverse dependence of reaction rate on $[H^+]$ ¹⁴. The same observation has been made in the oxidation of acidic amino acids by hypobromous acid (Table 1). Of the remaining two, HOBr and not NBN should be the oxidizing species, since the rate is also inverse function of nicotinamide concentration. A plot of

inverse of the observed rate constant against the nicotinamide concentration is linear ($r = 0.9920$).

The retardation of the rate of oxidation with added nicotinamide suggests that the pre-equilibrium step involves a process in which nicotinamide is one of the products [eq. (2)]. Another possible reaction, disproportionation of NBN to *N,N*-dibromonicotinamide, can be ruled out in view of the strict first order dependence of the reaction rate on NBN. Thus the most likely oxidizing species is HOBr¹².

In acid medium, amino acid exists in its protonated form (SH^+) which is resistant to attack by NBN. It is observed that the rate has inverse dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$. Thus the only species possibly controlling the rate of oxidation seems to be $\text{RCH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{COOH}$.

It is a well known fact that in acid medium amino acids exist in a mixture of zwitter-ionic and cationic form. Cationic forms of amino acids can be considered to be the reactive species in acid medium. The attack of NBN on the α -carbon of zwitter-ionic form of amino acid is more feasible since it has relatively lower electron density than the anionic form¹⁵.

The first order dependence on [substrate] and [oxidant] reveals that overall rate may involve the interaction of HOBr and amino acid in the rate determining step. But first order in the [substrate] and a definite intercept in the $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{sub}]$ plot, suggest that the decomposition of the complex formed from the substrate and HOBr is the rate determining step as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Here $\text{R} = (\text{CH}_2)\text{OH}$ for Ser and $\text{CH}_3(\text{CHOH})$ for Thr.

The rate law for the above mechanism may be divided as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{NBN}]}{dT} \\ &= k_d [\text{Complex}] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$= \frac{k_d k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{NBN}][\text{SH}^+]}{k_{-1} k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{NA}][\text{H}^+]} \quad (9)$$

$$[\text{NBN}]_T = [\text{NBN}] + [\text{HOBr}] + [\text{Complex}] \quad (10)$$

$$= [\text{NBN}] + \frac{k_1 [\text{NBN}]}{k_{-1} [\text{NA}]} +$$

$$\frac{k_d k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{NBN}][\text{SH}^+]}{k_{-1} k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{NA}][\text{H}^+]} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{[\text{NBN}]_T}{k_{-1} [\text{NA}] + k_1 + \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{SH}^+]}{k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{H}^+]}} = [\text{NBN}] \quad (12)$$

Substituting $[\text{NBN}]$ in eq. (9)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{-d[\text{NBN}]_T}{dT} &= \\ &= \frac{k_d k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{NBN}]_T [\text{SH}^+]}{k_{-1} k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{NA}][\text{H}^+] + k_{-1} k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{H}^+] + k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{SH}^+]} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

On rearranging the equation

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{k_{-1} k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{NA}][\text{H}^+]}{k_d k_1 k_2 k_3} + \frac{k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{H}^+]}{k_d k_2 k_3} \right] \frac{1}{[\text{SH}^+]} + \\ \frac{1}{k_d} = \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The rate-determining step proposed in the above mechanism predicts negligible salt effect which has been experimentally observed.

The formation of the complex involves the charge separation which leads to a negative solvent effect. This

has been confirmed by the increase in rate with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. The involvement of amino acid molecule in the rate-determining step leads to different values of k_{obs} for different initial concentrations of amino acids under study, namely, serine and threonine.

The proposed mechanism is well supported by the moderate values of energy of activation and thermodynamic parameters. The negative entropy of activation indicates the complex formation as suggested in the above reaction mechanism, and also indicates that the complex is more ordered than reactants¹⁶. High positive values of the free energy of activation and the enthalpy of activation show that the transition state is highly solvated.

Experimental

The amino acids (A.R., Loba) were used as such. Standard solution of NBN (m.p. 210 °C) was prepared afresh in water and its purity was checked iodometrically. Hydrochloric acid (AnalaR) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Sodium perchlorate (Merck) was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Acetic acid (A.R., Qualigen) was purified by standard method¹⁷. Mercuric acetate was added to suppress the formation of free bromine which otherwise would have vitiated the results. Mercuric acetate did not interfere with the results¹⁸. Conductivity water was used throughout the study. Other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

The reaction was carried out under pseudo-first order condition ($[\text{amino acid}] \gg [\text{NBN}]$). The reaction was followed potentiometrically by setting up a cell made up of the reaction mixture into which the platinum electrode and reference electrode (SCE) were dipped. The e.m.f of the cell was measured periodically using a Equip-Tronics (EQ-DGD) potentiometer. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed from the plots of $\log(E_t - E_\infty)$ against time were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. The course of the reaction was studied for more than two half-lives.

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

A mixture of amino acid (0.01 mol dm^{-3}), NBN (0.05 mol dm^{-3}) and HCl (0.8 mol dm^{-3}) was made upto 100 ml with water and acetic acid mixture (1 : 1). After the reaction was complete, the excess of NBN was determined iodometrically, and several determinations with

various amino acids indicated 1 : 1 stoichiometry. The overall stoichiometry of the oxidation reaction may be represented as

In a typical experiment, a mixture of amino acid (Ser and Thr, 1 mol dm^{-3}) and NBN ($1.5 \text{ g}, 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was made up to 50 ml with acetic acid-water mixture (1 : 1) in presence of HCl (0.8 mol dm^{-3}). The mixture was allowed to stand for 12 h in the dark to ensure completion of the reaction. It was then treated with an excess (125 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in HCl (2 mol dm^{-3}) and set aside for 10 h. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, recrystallised from ethanol (80%). The product was found identical (m.p. and m.m.p.) with an authentic sample of DNP of glycolaldehyde and 2-hydroxypropionaldehyde respectively¹⁹. Carbon dioxide and ammonia were detected by baryta water and Nessler's reagent respectively. The presence of corresponding aldehyde and ammonium ions were also confirmed by the spot tests²⁰ with chromotropic acid and *p*-nitrobenzene-diazonium chloride respectively.

Conclusion :

The rate of the reaction depends on the first power of concentration of H^+ and oxidant. Added nicotinamide retards the reaction. Addition of salts to the reaction medium has no effect on the rate. Increase in temperature increases the rate of reaction. The activation parameters are evaluated from the study of oxidation at different temperatures. The products obtained in each case (the corresponding aldehydes) were isolated and characterized.

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Pushpalatha *et al.* : Oxidative kinetics of serine and threonine by *N*-bromonicotinamide

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